

THE CONSORTIUM

Coordinated by CEA Leti, the SARAH consortium brings together leading industries, universities, research centres and technology providers.

<small>CEA LETI</small> 		
<small>TYOTERVEYSLAITOS</small> 		
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<small>FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION</small> 		

USER-CENTRED CIVIL
INFRASTRUCTURE RELIABLE
ASSESSMENT AND HEALING

LET'S CONNECT

Follow us for more insight and exchange;
we are looking forward!

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picture: POMA

THE CHALLENGE

OUR SOLUTION

Transforming how Europe **inspects**, **maintains** and **repairs** its critical civil infrastructure.

EUROPEAN CONSORTIUM

HUMAN-CENTERED DIGITAL SOLUTION

CIVIL INFRASTRUCTURE

SARAH adopts a human-centred approach to develop a **safe-by-design integrated digital solution** that supports maintenance and repair decision and planning, order, intervention and reporting. Leveraging metaverse technologies and egocentric augmented reality solutions, the system empowers infrastructure supervisors and intervention workers by providing real-time assistance, fostering skill development, and improving their Occupational Safety and Health.

picture: Canva

“Preserving the value and safety of Europe’s civil infrastructure requires smarter tools -

That’s where SARAH comes in. We are proud to contribute to this initiative aimed at transforming the infrastructure management across Europe, with economical and societal impacts.”

Sébastien Boisseau
lab manager at CEA Leti

Major disasters (e.g. Ponte Morandi, 2018) highlighted the critical condition of many European civil infrastructures due to inadequate maintenance, unforeseen operating conditions, and extended usage. Regular inspections of all types of infrastructures are essential to assess their health, guide maintenance and repair, and extend service life.

IDENTIFICATION

INSPECTION

ASSESSMENT

REPAIR

REPORTING